

Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary school Teachers: Basis for an Intervention Plan

¹Mary Daphne P. Silvestre
Bukidnon State University

Abstract:- This study assessed the multitasking practices of public secondary school teachers: Basis for an Intervention Plan Bukidnon National High School, Division of Malaybalay City during the school year 2013-2014. The practices were categorized as instructional expert, classroom manager, coach in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities, and meeting professional responsibilities. Descriptive method of research was employed using a researcher-made questionnaire as the main data gathering tool. Slovin's formula was used to determine the sample of one hundred forty-three teachers and two hundred ninety-five students as respondents. Stratified random sampling was used in identifying the teachers as respondents in the main school and purposive sampling for the annex schools. The respondents were chosen objectively because of their school size. Mean, standard deviation, percentage, were used to treat the data. Findings revealed that the multitasking practices of the teachers as instructional expert, classroom manager, coach in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities, and meeting professional responsibilities were done to a great extent.

Keywords: *Multitasking Practices, Instructional Expert, Classroom Manager, Coach In Co-Curricular And Extra-Curricular Activities.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-tasking is a prevailing practice among teachers nowadays. It is an indicator, which shows that teachers are skillful in instruction that improves student's achievement (Bernat, 2008). In spite of the volume of work in teaching, teachers are expected to carry out other activities with a reasonable degree of initiative and resourcefulness as the Department of Education released an order to address the need to intensify learning outcomes among students (Luistro, 2011).

In the Department of Education (Dep Ed), multitasking practices of teachers include teaching the students and managing the classroom as to the physical aspect incorporating with it discipline. Then leading the students towards new skills and doing paper works as required by the department.

Luistro (2012) stated that beginning school year 2012-2013 teachers of all public elementary and secondary schools should have more time for the preparation of necessary support of instructional materials and student centered activities. The Dep Ed adopts flexibility in the

preparation of daily lesson. Through these reasons multitasking is an important factor to be taken into consideration.

Previous authors indicated that teachers are doing multifarious activities related to the teaching (Lardizabal, 2008). They practiced multitasking as instructional experts and counselors (Alima, 2010). They are involved in multifarious activities, which focus on instructional performance (Billiones, 2004).

As practiced, teachers in BNHS were very active in improving students' performance. Students are national achievers and almost always bring honor and recognition for the school. However, when it comes to students' performance in the NAT, the result only show an *average mastery* considering that it is the biggest school in the province with updated instruction and school facilities. It is for this reason that the researcher is interested to conduct the study to find out what problems do teachers have, as they undergo their multifarious tasks.

The present study, focus on the multitasking of public secondary school teachers: Basis for an Intervention Plan. Teachers tasks as instructional experts, classroom manager, coach in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities, are assessed.

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

This study is anchored on the concept of Moore (2001), which states that teachers perform multitasking practices in school specifically as an instructional expert. As an instructional expert, the task of the teacher includes: planning, presenting, and evaluating the learning of the students (Kelly, 2012).

In planning the lesson the teacher needs to prepare what topic the students will tackle and anticipate the instructional materials to be utilized. This follows a time frame so that the lesson will be attained. In presenting the lesson the teachers are also tasked to make use of strategies with specific student's activity to engage students learning. Then, in evaluating the learning of the students the teacher is also tasked to prepare test questions following the table of specification, to have a proper distribution of the test item based on the levels of learning needed to be enhanced.

Kounin (1977) revealed that teachers as classroom manager have the ability in dealing with overlapping activities or to multitask which is tied to withitness. Multitasking in teaching is the act of doing multiple things

related to the job at once. It is often encouraged among teachers, since teachers have an important impact on the students achievement (Lloyd et.al.2000). It is believed that

multitasking is more effective than focusing a single task at once (Smith, 2013).

Fig 1 Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework of the Study

Figure 1 shows the schema on the conceptual framework of the study. The first box contains the independent variables of the study consisting of the four concepts of the multitasking practices of public secondary school teachers. These include: teachers as instructional experts with the sub components as a

Lesson planner, lesson developer, lesson organizer, lesson evaluator, and record keeper, classroom manager (Kounnin,1977); coach in co-curricular activities and extra-curricular activities (Garbarino,1997); and have the tasks of meeting professional responsibilities (Lardizabal, et al.2000). The second box contains the dependent variable, which is the National Achievement Test scores of students in the core subjects: English, Science, Filipino and Araling Panlipunan.

The teacher as an *instructional expert* is expected to prepare lesson plans, which is the detailed description of the course instruction to get optimum result in teaching. As an instructional expert, the teacher is tasked to act as a lesson planner. Teachers also prepare alternative activities for those who are absent during the class, and assessment, which includes group activity, homework and test, were also some of the diverse tasks of the teacher (Bridgeland, et al., 2009).

As a developer of the lesson, the teacher selects the general topic; decide what goals would be fitted to the students according to the intellect, attitude and values orientation of the students and the different skills. The teacher follows the tasks as a lesson evaluator.

Being record keepers of student's performance is also one of the tasks of a teacher. This serves as basis in giving due grades to the learner. Teachers also do the computation of the grades and filling papers like the form 1 and 2, class record.

The third task of a teacher, which made multitasking prevalent, is being *a coach*. The teacher as a coach also needs to study, plan, and develop strategies that would help develop students' self-confidence to be able to win in the competition's, report cards, form 137 and the form 18.

The fourth task of teachers is *meeting professional responsibilities*. These are activities, which are done after class hours that require the close supervision of the teacher. The teacher needs to spare some time for planning the activity, working to materialize the assigned task, and supervising the students in the program of activities.

This study assessed the multitasking practices of teachers: Basis for an Intervention during the school year 2012-2013.

Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

- What is the extent of multitasking practice of the secondary school teachers of Bukidnon National High School and annex schools considering the following criteria:
 - ✓ Instructional expert;
 - ✓ Classroom manager;
 - ✓ Coach in Co-curricular/Extra-Curricular Activities; and
 - ✓ Meeting professional responsibilities?

II. METHODOLOGY

A descriptive method of research is used in the study. It assessed the extent of multitasking practices of Public Secondary School Teachers. Basis for an Intervention in the Central District of the Division of Malaybalay City in the school year 2013-2014. It included eight departments, namely: Filipino, English, Science, Mathematics, Araling Panlipunan, TLE Department, MAPEH, and Values Education. The focus is on the prevailing conditions of

multitasking of teachers and the NAT achievement of the students.

The respondents of the study were the one hundred and forty-three (143) teachers including the Department Heads of the main and annex school. In the main school they were the teachers from the different departments teaching the

different subjects from grade seven to fourth year curriculum. Then the teachers from the annex schools were those who teach different subjects from grade seven to fourth year. Slovin’s formula was used to determine the number of teachers who served as the respondents. Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents of the study.

Table 1 Containing the Scale Range of Intervals, Descriptive Rating and Qualifying Description is Illustrated as follows

Scale	Range of Intervals	Qualitative Description	Qualifying Statement
5	4.21-5.00	Very Great Extent	If the teacher ALWAYS practice Multitasking.
4	3.41-4.20	Great Extent	If the teacher practice ALMOST ALWAYS Multitasking.
3	2.61-3.40	Moderate Extent	When the teacher practices SOMETIMES multitasking.
2	1.81-2.60	Low Extent	When the teacher practice SELDOM Multitasking.
1	1.00-1.80	Very low Extent	When the teacher practice NEVER practiced multitasking.

➤ *Treatment of the Data*

In analyzing the data to be gathered, the researcher used the following statistical measures:

To answer problem 1, the mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of multitasking practices of public secondary school teachers as rated by the departments and the students.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

➤ *Instructional Expert*

Being an instructional expert necessitates teachers to face varied activities as one of the foremost tasks. These tasks include: lesson planner, lesson organizer, lesson developer, evaluator, and record keeper. Table 2 shows the extent of the multitasking practices of teachers as *instructional experts* specifically as lesson planner.

The indicator with the topmost mean is identifying the topic using the Desired Learning Competency (DLC), textbooks and other learning materials was practiced to *a very great extent*. This means that, the teachers practiced always multitasking. This finding was supported by Spady (1994) that the teachers were doing their varied tasks well as to the preparation of the lesson using the desired learning competency.

Table 2 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as a Planner Being an Instructional Expert

Practices	Mean	Sd	Qualitative Description
Identify a topic for the lesson base on the DLC, textbooks and other learning materials which consider student’s interest.	4.46	.65	Very Great Extent
Present the lesson using varied strategies to meet the learning needs of the students.	4.24	.67	Very Great Extent
Identify specific contents such as vocabulary Points of grammar or language as prescribe by the course curriculum.	4.07	.69	Great Extent
Prepare relevant instructional Materials of the topic presented.	4.06	.72	Great Extent
Prepare a detailed description of the lesson to get an optimum result in teaching.	3.97	.80	Great Extent
Overall	4.16	.52	Great Extent

Since the preparation of the instructional materials is one of the important concerns of a teacher Nwadinigwe (2000) revealed that utilizing instructional materials is the only means that learners will be able to gain knowledge, skills habits, facts and ideas. To become more effective in multitasking the teacher may consider time management. Gapol (2004) revealed that to strengthen the work values Lardizabal, et al. (2004), asserted that the detailed setting up of the lesson is the vital function of being a teacher.

The procedure of presenting the lesson to the learners is the next concern of the teacher to plan. In this task the teacher needs to become systematic and draw out every skill that the students needed. First, the skill in motivating the students must be established to have a connection between the teacher and the learners. Ormrod (2010) stated that when students are well motivated, their interest would be boosted causing them to become guided, directed and participative in the lesson.

Table 3 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as an Organizer Being an Instructional Expert

Practices	Mean	Sd	Qualitative Description
Create a calendar of activities to Organize necessary measures for learning.	4.23	.70	Very Great Extent
Use discussion for what students do and /or like to do to elicit their Knowledge of the topic.	4.18	.69	Great Extent
Use homework review to organize the lesson from the previous to the present topic.	4.17	.67	Great Extent
Make visual aid and other instructional Materials that will enforce learning.	4.11	.79	Great Extent
Organize the activity of each lesson such as the time estimates, required materials and alternative activities for absent students during the class.	4.11	.72	Great Extent
Overall	4.14	.52	Great Extent

Among the indicators with least mean is on organizing the activity of each lesson such as the time estimates, required materials and alternative activities for absent students during the class, and on Making visual aid and other instructional Materials that will enforce learning. According to some of the department heads during the focused group discussion conducted last December 2013, this task adds to the bulk of paper works of teachers including the heads of every department since it is very it is a requirement included for the teachers to be cleared in school. The in-charge of each department needs to check the output of the teacher.

This finding may also mean that teachers were very creative of prioritizing their task through the use of the calendar of activities. It is of great help if teachers budget their time effectively. This finding is supported by Geolina (2012) who affirmed that in spite of the volume of work in

teaching, teachers are expected to carry out all instructional practices with reasonable degree of initiative and resourcefulness.

The teacher as a lesson organizer needs to look into how to organize a lesson designed for those who were absent during the session. Bridgeland et al. (2009) mentioned that 76% of the teachers placed most of the responsibility for the dropout problem on the students. This means that the teacher as a lesson organizer need to change what has been practiced.

Table 4 shows the extent of multitasking practices of public secondary school teachers as a lesson developer. The overall mean indicates that these tasks were performed to a *great extent*. It means that teachers almost always practiced these tasks.

Table 4 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as a lesson developer being an Instructional Expert

Practices	Mean	Sd	Qualitative Description
Provide input of the lesson through a form of example, explanations, and instruction using multimedia.	4.29	.69	Very Great Extent
Provide inputs from the learning Materials aside from other textbooks.	4.25	.68	Very Great Extent
Select a general topic and decide the goals Fitted to the student’s attitude, intellect and values.	4.09	.68	Great Extent
Develop an instructional material fitted to the needs of the learners.	4.04	.74	Great Extent
Present a strategy to help the students absorb the content of the lesson	4.03	.67	Great Extent
Overall	4.14	.55	Great Extent

Teachers were doing their varied tasks well as to the preparation of the lesson using the desired learning competency. This focused on the teaching instruction on the learning outcome of students. Although teachers are well provided with the prototype lesson still they need to multitask especially when the textbooks and other instructional materials needed in delivering the lesson are not available.

Presenting a strategy to help the students absorb the lesson is among the indicators with the least mean. These findings confirm that teachers are doing multitasking practices in using multimedia as an aid in the teaching instruction to help the learners. Berk, (2009) revealed that there are valuable outcomes of using multimedia in teaching as follows: grab students’ attention; focus students’ concentration; generate interest in class; create a sense of anticipation; energize or relax students for learning exercise; draw on students’ imagination; improve attitudes toward

content and learning; build a connection with other students and instructor; increase memory of content; increase understanding; foster creativity; stimulate the flow of ideas; Foster deeper learning; provide an opportunity for freedom of expression; serve as a vehicle for collaboration; inspire and motivate students. As posited by Muroski (2008) fitting together by the teacher and the students is the most active tactic in getting student’s interest in grasping the context. As posited by Muroski (2008) fitting together by the teacher and the students is the most active tactic in getting student’s interest in grasping the context.

Hans (2005) stated that teachers must possess the expertise of choosing effective instructional tools since it is vital in the teaching learning process. This is strengthened by Lardizabal (2004) that preparing the best suited instructional material to the topic is also important to reach a higher level of learning.

Table 5 shows the extent of multitasking practices of public secondary school teachers as a lesson evaluator. The teachers to a *very great extent* performed all the indicators. The overall result as an evaluator reveals that the teacher

always practice multitasking in appraising the output of the learners. The standard deviation shows that the responses of the respondents were close to each other.

Table 5 Extent of Multitasking practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as a Lesson Evaluator being an Instructional Expert

Practices	Mean	sd	Qualitative description
Evaluate the performance of the learners through quiz, unit test, and periodical exams	4.58	.65	Very Great Extent
Evaluate the learners by giving group Activities for practicum.	4.45	.65	Very Great Extent
Evaluate the performance of the learner through oral recitation.	4.31	.66	Very Great Extent
Reinforce the materials that was presented in the lesson for students comprehension and learning.	4.27	.69	Very Great Extent
Evaluate the learners by giving remarks/ Comments emphasizing the strength as well As the improvement of the learner	4.26	.73	Very Great Extent
Overall	4.37	.52	Very Great Extent

Evaluating students’ performance is done in different ways. This could be taken from board work activities, seatwork, homework, quizzes, chapter test, actual performance or practicum and even in making the project. As stated by Dr. Zint (MEERA,2012) a cautiously estimated assessment can obtain high improvement in student’s performance.

conduct counteractive activities that would enhance the learning of those who are left behind.

Gregorio (2005) asserted that if teachers constantly follow up the activities and output of the students, gradual learner’s development would be monitored properly and

Table 6 shows the extent of multitasking practices of secondary teachers as record keepers. As reflected in the Table, the overall mean is described as practiced by the teachers *to a very great extent*. The standard deviation indicates that the ratings of the respondents are close to each other. The task that tops the list is teachers keeping record of students’ class participation and recitation.

Table 6 Extent of Multitasking practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as a Record Keeper Being an Instructional Expert

Practices	Mean	sd	Qualitative Description
Record students participation or Recitation in the class	4.72	.58	Very Great Extent
Record student’s scores in quizzes Unit test and periodical test.	4.68	.66	Very Great Extent
Compute recorded quizzes, unit test and periodical test.	4.60	.80	Very Great Extent
Record the misbehavior of students in the class through the anecdotal record, and the tracking and tracing system.	.4.15	.90	Great Extent
Overall	4.54	.52	Very Great Extent

The task being a record keeper requires a teacher to extend his time for instruction even at home since recording and computing always go together. The time allotted for paper works is a maximum of two hours, which is not sufficient (R.A.4670). Calmorin and Magallanes (2003) said that the teachers are able to manage well as record keepers. Time is wisely spent taking attendance, recording grades, and following through on all necessary recordkeeping tasks (Kelly,2010).

except one which means that this particular indicator needs to be enhanced by the teacher to further follow-up the student as to their academic performance, learning.

Sanford (2010) mentioned that record management is concerned with managing records for information and evidence purpose. Salandanan (2005) asserted that record keeping is an essential task of a teacher that needs to be done consistently and effectively.

The anecdotal record made the teacher gives unbiased judgment about the students (Kinra, 2008). This record is supposed to help the student form a clear view of his behavior in the classroom.

➤ *The Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as Classroom Manager*

As a classroom manager it is the task of the teacher to establish a non-compelling atmosphere in teaching that includes the tasks as a classroom organizer and being lead teachers. Table 8 shows the extent of multitasking practices of teachers as lead teachers in classroom management. The overall mean shows that teachers practiced these tasks *to a great extent*. The standard deviation indicates homogeneity of responses.

Martinez (2002) posited that teachers were performing very satisfactorily in assessing the learning outcome of the students, which might have been an upshot of the multitasking practices of teachers. As a record keeper almost all indicators was rated by the teacher to a *very great extent*,

The task with the highest mean is on developing a caring and supportive atmosphere among teachers and students. This was practiced to a *very great extent*. This indicates that teachers always practice multitasking of becoming helpful and concerned with the learners and the co-teachers. These are characteristics which is habitually carried out among teachers (Torralba,2012).

Table 7 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as a Lead Teacher Being a Classroom Manager

Practices	Mean	sd	Qualitative Description
Develop caring and supportive relationship among teachers and students.	4.26	.64	Very Great Extent
Use group management to encourage Students with academic task	3.98	.85	Great Extent
Observe department members in the classroom as to strategy and instructional materials.	3.77	.95	Great Extent
Orient other teachers aside from working on own classroom.	3.61	1.03	Great extent
Serve as liaison officer between the Teachers and the principal	.3.59	1.06	Great Extent
Overall	3.84	.65	Great Extent

Evertson and Weinstein (2006) revealed that sanitation and well-organized classroom promotes a vital effect to the students learning experience and improve societal and personal relationship towards others.

Kuonnin,(1977) posited that a classroom manager focuses not only the physical environment but also to integrate educational and disciplinary aspects in the classroom

➤ *The Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as Coach in Co-Curricular and Extra-Curricular Activities*

As shown in Table 8, teachers are already superb in motivating students to practice more and develop new skills since it was done by them to a *very great extent*.

Table 8 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as an Encourager in Coaching Co-Curricular and Extra- Curricular Activities

Practices	Mean	sd	Qualitative Description
Motivate the students to practice more and develop a new skills.	4.38	.74	Very Great Extent
Guide the students strive for improvement	4.37	.73	Very Great Extent
Develop strategies to help students increase more self- confidence.	4.35	.70	Very Great Extent
Motivate student/athlete to engage in and have equal participation in all activities during the practice.	4.20	.84	Great Extent
Help the students in athletic goals when discourage during the competition	4.13	.86	Great Extent
Overall	4.28	.65	Very Great Extent

As an encourager in coaching, teachers need to have proper training on how to assist the students in times of discouragement to help them refocus and build again self-esteem. Dwyer (1992) mentioned that motivating the students to be engaged in a competition or sports is the most rewarding role being a coach.

Table 9 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as a Protector in Coaching Co-Curricular and Extra-Curricular Activities

Practices	Mean	sd	Qualitative Description
Orient students on safety precautions especially on weather related issues and keep the student away from hazards during practice.	4.28	.84	Very Great Extent
Care for athletic injuries using physical Therapy techniques, medication, and applying preventive and protective measures.	3.83	1 .07	Great Extent
Evaluate athlete /students readiness to play and provide participation clearance	3.81	1.09	Great Extent
Ensure that the students will not become over fatigue during practice.	3.81	1.06	Great Extent
Conduct an initial assessment on the athletes Illness in order to provide emergency or Continued care.	3.73	1.07	Great Extent
Overall	3.89	.90	Great Extent

In view of the fact that it is the responsibility of the teacher to keep the students in school it is also embedded in his duty to look after the safety of the students even after school hours especially in scheduled practice for any competition. Snyder, et al. (2011) asserted that being a coach necessitates not just a mere teacher but a competent teammate. The teacher is not just a coach but also a member of the group who is concerned with his companions.

As revealed in Table 9, the task of conducting an initial assessment on the athletes' illness in order to provide emergency or continued care got the lowest rating. As a teacher/coach it is his duty to assist the athlete that they will not get ill before the practice, during the practice and after the practice or competition.

Table 10 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as a Trainer in Coaching Co-Curricular and Extra-Curricular Activities

Practices	Mean	sd	Qualitative Description
Devote time during and after classroom Instruction to assist students performance.	4.03	.93	Great Extent
Keep complete record of students' performance during the practice	3.98	1.01	Great Extent
Orient students for clarity as to the goals and strategies to win in the competition.	3.96	.95	Great Extent
Asses from the start of practice students improvement in acquiring necessary skills for the activity through a one on one session	3.96	.95	Great Extent
Schedule warm ups, proper execution of the skills to make the muscles and the brain function effectively.	3.84	1.06	Great Extent
Asses students progress beyond classroom instruction time.	3.95	.93	Great Extent
Provide models and examples of excellent actions, video tapes to motivate students learning.	3.80	.99	Great Extent
Overall	3.91	.85	Great Extent

Section 13 of the *Magna Carta* for teachers stated that teachers will spend six (6) hours for the actual teaching and the rest of the two (2) hours is for the paper works.

Table 11 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as an Advisor in Coaching Co-Curricular and Extra-Curricular Activities

Practice	Mean	sd	Qualitative Description
Give a friendly advice to set the mental Condition of the students and to give words of encouragement to boost their interest.	4.40	.87	Very Great Extent
Advice students to work harder and provide a sense of belonging and direction	4.26	.82	Very Great Extent
Serve as adviser of the students to different School competition, academic and extra-Curricular activities.	3.89	1.14	Great Extent
Serve as an adviser/ facilitator of skill related activities like music, art, sports, literary arts, dance and photography.	3.81	1.16	Great Extent
Seek financial assistance to defray students expenses in food, materials during the practice and final competition	3.70	1.12	Great Extent
Overall	4.04	.74	Great Extent

As revealed in table, the highest mean is on the tasks of giving a friendly advice to set the mental condition of the students and to give words of encouragement to boost their interest; and giving advice to students to work harder and provide a sense of belonging and direction. Both tasks were done to a *very great extent*. With adequate training, and a systematic way of recognizing and rewarding performance coaches would be motivated to do their tasks (Gordon & Habley, 2000).

➤ *The Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers in Meeting Professional Responsibilities*

To ensure students support in meeting professional responsibilities, it is essential that teachers fill up the necessary information needed to be written in the tracking and tracing system as a kind of an anecdotal record. Table 13 shows the extent of multitasking practices of teachers as support in meeting professional responsibilities. The overall mean shows that the tasks were practiced to a *great extent*. The standard deviation shows that there are variations of scores from the mean.

Table 12 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as Student Support in Meeting Professional Responsibilities

Practices	Mean	sd	Qualitative Description
Fill up and submit the tracking and tracing System of students.	3.76	1.19	Great Extent
Sponsoring interest focus activities such as School choir, marching band, food technology Team, dance club, literary club, visual art club, Photography, drama club and rondalla.	3.38	1.30	Moderate Extent
sponsoring academic focus activities like the school paper, school governing council, student government, debate team and quiz team.	3.27	1.22	Moderate extent
sponsoring athletic focus activities such as Individual sports, team sports and cheerleading.	3.20	1.29	Moderate Extent
Overall	3.53	.95	Great Extent

This supports the finding of Miller-Power (1996) that monitoring and recording students behavior and achievement in the class could lead teachers in assessing students learning. Johnston, (2003) observed that students' performance and behavior would help teachers address students learning needs.

Table 13 Extent of Multitasking Practices of Public Secondary School Teachers as professional Development

Practices	Mean	sd	Qualitative Description
Submit requirements, financial report, and narrative report for the school clearance	4.75	.53	Very Great extent
Attend department meetings, school conference and division conferences	4.68	.60	Very Great Extent
Attend teachers forum, In –service trainings, seminar-workshops and leadership development program.	4.66	.62	Very Great Extent
Participate in classroom, department, school and division programs.	4.62	.65	Very Great Extent
Submit data analysis for the improvement of professional practices such as pre-test, post- test, periodic test, mean, TOS and item analysis.	4.58	.69	Very Great Extent
Submit on time calendar of activities teacher improvement plan, CB-PAST,NCBTS, teachers individual program, monthly school register and club accomplishment report.	4.44	.67	Very Great Extent
Prepare necessary documents and other data for the teachers portfolio.	4.36	.73	Very Great Extent
Provide necessary updated data needed for the school (SBM) program.	4.36	.73	Very Great Extent
Examine students work through display and culminating programs	4.35	.77	Very Great Extent
Attend retreat, meditation and mentoring activities that would promote professional growth	4.20	.82	Great Extent
Overall	4.40	.51	Very Great Extent

The indicator with the highest mean is on the submission of requirements, financial reports and narrative report for the school clearance. This is rated as performed by teachers to a very great extent. This indicates that teachers were doing multitasking practices always.

Henry & Roseberry (2001) revealed that the purpose of these reports and requirements is to investigate a problem or a need, find workable solution, and make recommendations. When the teachers submit promptly the necessary reports on the students' performance, narrative reports on the accomplishment of a club, clearance and all-important documents needed by the administration, it would be easy for them to examine the problems encountered by the teachers, students, and the parents.

➤ *Findings:*

The salient findings of the study are as follows:

- The multitasking practices of teachers as instructional experts, classroom managers, coaches in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities and in meeting professional responsibilities were done by the teachers to a great extent.
- The fourth-year students have an *average mastery* in their NAT scores in the core subjects namely: English, Science, Math, Filipino and Araling Panlipunan.
- There is no significant relationship between the multitasking practices of the teachers and the NAT scores of the students.

IV. CONCLUSION

➤ *Base from the Findings of the Study, the Following Conclusions are Derived:*

- Since the teachers practice multitasking to a *great extent*, therefore they perform multitasking practices almost always as instructional experts, classroom managers, coaches in co-curricular/extra-curricular activities and in meeting the professional responsibilities.
- Since the NAT scores of the students is on *average mastery*, therefore the students lack necessary skills to move towards mastery.
- Since there is no significant relationship between the multitasking practices of the teachers and the NAT scores of the students, therefore the multitasking practices of the teachers did not affect the students' scores in the NAT.

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